

An Automated Planning Approach for Personalized Robot-Aided Rehabilitation Sessions

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Abstract—Robot-aided rehabilitation is increasingly recognized for its potential to restore functionality and improve the quality of life for individuals with neurological or musculoskeletal conditions. Personalized treatment is crucial in Healthcare 5.0, employing reactive methods for immediate assistance and feedback and deliberative approaches that strategically plan sessions based on therapeutic goals.

This paper proposes a cognitive architecture for a robot-aided rehabilitation platform based on Kahneman’s dual-system theory. It integrates automated planning techniques to tailor session exercises to individual user conditions and clinical objectives, optimizing therapeutic outcomes. By combining automated planning with real-time monitoring and feedback mechanisms, the proposed framework enhances the personalization of robot-aided rehabilitation interventions.

Index Terms—Robot-aided rehabilitation, Physical rehabilitation, Automated Planning, Task Planning.

I. INTRODUCTION

Physical rehabilitation is crucial for restoring functionality and enhancing the quality of life in individuals with neurological or musculoskeletal conditions. Rehabilitation robots play a pivotal role by delivering intensive treatments, implementing diverse care approaches, integrating feedback systems for gamified exercises, and objectively assessing patients’ motor performance [1]. Personalization enhances engagement and motor recovery and can be implemented reactively, offering real-time assistance and feedback, and deliberatively, recommending tailored rehabilitation plans aligned with recovery goals [2].

Automatic planning techniques have revolutionized robotic rehabilitation by creating tailored exercise schedules based on patient assessments to achieve specific session goals. These techniques are used in clinical scales where robots autonomously evaluate pose accuracy and compile assessment sheets [3]. In pediatric neurorehabilitation, similar methods engage children through interactive games that adjust error thresholds for personalized therapy [4]. However, current systems lack comprehensive monitoring to evaluate plan efficacy.

Therefore, there is a critical need for a control architecture in robotic rehabilitation systems that personalizes treatment

This work was supported by the Italian Ministry of Research, under the complementary actions to the NRRP “Fit4MedRob - Fit for Medical Robotics” Grant (PNC0000007), (CUP: B53C22006990001).

based on patient conditions and therapist-set clinical objectives [5]. This architecture should integrate real-time monitoring and feedback mechanisms to adapt the treatment plan, ensuring alignment with the patient’s progress and therapeutic goals. By addressing both reactive and deliberative personalization, such a system would enhance rehabilitation effectiveness, providing tailored and responsive care to meet specific patient needs.

Therefore, this work aims to propose a cognitive architecture for the automatic planning of robot-mediated rehabilitation sessions that can consider clinical objectives, exploit a clinical knowledge base, and leverage low- and high-level control loops for plan refinement.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

Fig. 1. Cognitive architecture for the automated approach for robot-aided rehabilitation session planning

Fig. 1 illustrates the proposed cognitive architecture for automated robot-aided rehabilitation session planning, integrating high- and low-level control layers for personalized treatments. The therapist initiates session planning based on the patient’s assessment, setting goals and constraints. The *Session Planner* uses a *Knowledge Base* of exercises to generate an optimized, tailored *Plan*. The reactive layer manages the *Sense* module, in charge of collecting multimodal data, and the *Act* module, triggering robotic actions such as real-time feedback and/or physical assistance as needed. The sensed information is also sent back to the *Session Planner* enabling dynamic adjustments of the plan based on the patient’s progress or condition changes.

In this framework, the *Knowledge Base* serves as the central data repository, maintaining patient profiles and a list of 23

rehabilitation exercises extracted from the "PhysioTherapy eXercises" database [6]. Each exercise is described by its intensity level, ensuring a range of intensities to engage all major muscle groups (see Table I).

TABLE I
LIST OF THE EXERCISES IMPLEMENTED IN THE KNOWLEDGE BASE
ALONG WITH THEIR INTENSITIES (I)

Exercise	I	Exercise	I
a_1	1	Frontal lunges	3
a_2	1	Squat	3
a_3	1	Military press	3
a_4	1	Side lunges	3
a_5	1	Butt kicks	3
a_6	1	Boxing	4
a_7	1	High knees	4
a_8	1	Jumping jacks	4
a_9	2	High kick	4
a_{10}	2	Jump squats	5
a_{11}	3	Running in place	5
a_{12}	3		

This information is crucial for the *Session Planner* which is the reasoning component that determines the sequence of physical exercises for rehabilitation sessions using timeline-based planning and numeric reasoning. It extends the PLAT-INUm framework with a heuristic search to evaluate the clinical qualities of partial plans, taking clinical objectives and the number of exercises as input [7]. The planner's goal is to create a plan (π) with sufficient stimuli, either by the number of exercises or the session duration specified by the clinician. It employs two search strategies to minimize or maximize the cumulative plan intensity ($\Sigma PI = \sum_{i=1}^N I_i$, where i iterates on the N exercises selected in the current plan) following [5].

A. Experimental Validation

To validate the ability of the *Session Planner* to generate effective plans that either minimize or maximize ΣPI , an experiment was conducted. The planner created ten "LOW" intensity plans (minimizing ΣPI) and ten "HIGH" intensity plans (maximizing ΣPI), each consisting of ten exercises. The ΣPI itself was computed for each plan to assess the effectiveness in achieving the desired intensity levels.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Fig 2 shows a heatmap of exercise plans generated by the *Session Planner* for LOW- and HIGH-intensity objectives, with darker shades indicating higher I levels. The most frequently used exercises in the LOW-intensity plans include a_1 , a_5 , and a_{10} , chosen for their focus on stretching and low-impact movements to engage muscles and improve flexibility gently. Conversely, the HIGH-intensity plans commonly feature a_{19} , a_{20} , and a_{23} , which are cardio-intensive activities aimed at elevating the heart rate and providing a robust cardiovascular workout. This distribution highlights how the planner strategically selects exercises to meet the desired intensity levels for each plan.

The mean ΣPI are 19.8 ± 2.4 for LOW- and 33.0 ± 2.2 for HIGH-intensity plans. A Mann-Whitney U test yielded a

Fig. 2. Graphical representation of the plans automatically generated by the proposed session planner given the LOW- and HIGH-intensity objectives.

p -value $< 10^{-3}$, indicating a statistically significant difference between the plans. These results demonstrate that the proposed *Session Planner* effectively tailors exercise intensity to meet specified goals, successfully distinguishing between LOW and HIGH-intensity requirements and providing personalized rehabilitation plans.

IV. CONCLUSION

This paper aimed to develop and validate a cognitive architecture for a robot-aided rehabilitation platform that delivers personalized treatment through automated planning techniques. The goal was to create tailored exercise plans based on individual user conditions and clinical objectives. Our experiments demonstrated the effectiveness of the *Session Planner* in generating customized plans that meet specific intensity goals.

Overall, this work offers a promising approach to integrating high-level reasoning and real-time feedback in robot-aided rehabilitation, paving the way for more responsive and individualized patient care. Future research will focus on expanding exercise options, refining planning algorithms, and conducting clinical trials.

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